

Nanoparticles-Protein Hybrid Based Magnetic Liposome

Amlan Kumar Das, Avinash Marwal, Vikram Pareek

I. INTRODUCTION

Abstract—Liposome plays an important role in medical and pharmaceutical science as e.g. nano scale drug carriers. Liposomes are vesicles of varying size consisting of a spherical lipid bilayer and an aqueous inner compartment. Magnet-driven liposome used for the targeted delivery of drugs to organs and tissues. These liposome preparations contain encapsulated drug components and finely dispersed magnetic particles.

Liposomes are vesicles of varying size consisting of a spherical lipid bilayer and an aqueous inner compartment that are generated *in vitro*. These are useful in terms of biocompatibility, biodegradability, and low toxicity, and can control biodistribution by changing the size, lipid composition, and physical characteristics. Furthermore, liposomes can entrap both hydrophobic and hydrophilic drugs and are able to continuously release the entrapped substrate, thus being useful drug carriers. Magnetic liposomes (MLs) are phospholipid vesicles that encapsulate magnetic or paramagnetic nanoparticles. They are applied as contrast agents for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI).

The biological synthesis of nanoparticles using plant extracts plays an important role in the field of nanotechnology. Green-synthesized magnetite nanoparticles-protein hybrid has been produced by treating Iron (III) / Iron (II) chloride with the leaf extract of *Datura innoxia*. The phytochemicals present in the leaf extracts act as a reducing as well stabilizing agents preventing agglomeration, which include flavonoids, phenolic compounds, cardiac glycosides, proteins and sugars.

The magnetite nanoparticles-protein hybrid has been trapped inside the aqueous core of the liposome prepared by reversed phase evaporation (REV) method using oleic and linoleic acid which has been shown to be driven under magnetic field confirming the formation magnetic liposome (ML). Chemical characterization of stealth magnetic liposome has been performed by breaking the liposome and release of magnetic nanoparticles. The presence iron has been confirmed by colour complex formation with KSCN and UV-Vis study using spectrophotometer Cary 60, Agilent.

This magnet driven liposome using nanoparticles-protein hybrid can be a smart vesicles for the targeted drug delivery.

Keywords—Nanoparticles-Protein Hybrid, Magnetic Liposome.

LIPOSOME represents dominant classes of nanocarriers capable of efficiently encapsulating and delivering a variety of drugs [1]. Hence liposome is vesicular systems that are formed when phospholipids are dispersed in an aqueous solution and self-assemble into one (unilamellar) or more (oligolamellar, multilamellar) concentric bilayers surrounding an aqueous core [2]. Liposome ensures the targeted delivery of substances encapsulated in the vesicles such as drugs and provide for a prolonged release of such substances. The increasing interest in liposome is related to the unique combination of their physicochemical and biological properties manifested both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [3].

Biocompatibility and site specific delivery are the two major issues for magnetic nanoparticle in therapeutic applications [4]. Therefore the green method of synthesis of magnetic nanoparticles described here is easy, efficient, and eco-friendly in comparison to chemical-mediated synthesis [5]. The chemical synthesis involves toxic solvents, high pressure, energy and high temperature conversion and microbe involved synthesis is not feasible industrially due to its lab maintenance [6], [7].

The aim of the present study is to demonstrate the bio-reductive synthesis of protein coated magnetic nano-bio hybrid using leaf extracts of *Datura innoxia* plants and its encapsulation into liposome. The liposomes were characterized by chemical and physical methods using potassium thiocyanate (KSCN) and digital gauss meter respectively. At last a model along with a theory has been proposed for successful isolation of magnetic liposome from a mixture of solutions into pure state.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Preparation of Aqueous Leaf Extract of *Datura innoxia*

Fresh leaves of *Datura innoxia* were washed under running tap water to remove any debris and dust attached to the leaves and subsequently with millipore water 3–4 times [8]. Leaves were air dried for two weeks at room temperature (25°C). The dried leaves were finely powdered through grinding using Lumix grinder. The extract was prepared by taking 40 g of powdered leaves in a 500 mL round flask with 300 mL of sterile millipore water. Then the above was boiled for 10 min and sieved and filtered twice by using Whatman filter paper No 42. The filtrate was collected and stored at 4°C and used within a week. Small amount of filtrate was dried at 80°C and analyzed by FT-IR techniques [9].

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B. Nanoparticle Synthesis

Ferric (III) chloride, Ferrous (II) chloride and NaOH were purchased from CDH, and the aqueous leaves extract of *Datura innoxia* was used for the bio reduction process. To synthesize nanoparticles from *Datura innoxia* 0.53 gm of Ferrous chloride tetrahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, AR) and 1.11gm of Ferric chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, AR) after weighing is dissolved in 100ml of sterile deionised water in 250ml beaker. The mixture is heated at 80°C under mild stirring [10]. After 10 minutes when the plate of stirrer gets heated up, 5mL of the aqueous solution of leaf extract was added to the above solution drop wise. After few minutes the initial colour of the mixture becomes darker. Further 20 ml of 1M NaOH (0.8gms) was measured and dissolved with sterile deionised water in a beaker and added drop wise to the solution. A change in color of the colloidal solutions and precipitation occurred, confirming green synthesis of Ferric oxide (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles.

C. Magnetic Liposome Preparation

The aqueous magnetic fluid (1 ml) is first dispersed in 15 ml of chloroform and methanol mixture (2:1 v/v) containing Oleic acid and Linoleic acid mixture in molar ratio of 3:2. The mixture was kept under vigorous magnetic stirring for 15 min at room temperature to obtain unilamellar liposomes in water-oil emulsion (W/O). This emulsion is further introduced slowly in an excess of ultrapure water (100 ml) to obtain multiple emulsion W/O/W [11].

Vesicles were obtained by evaporation of chloroform/methanol from the microscopic oil spherules at 50°C. The flask is kept in warm bath under magnetic stirring to keep the spherules suspended. 0.9% NaCl is added for precipitation of uncapsulated magnetic nanoparticles [4].

D. Characterization of Magnetic Liposome

Confirmation of magnetic nanoparticles into liposomes was determined by using KSCN as follows: Aliquots of 4 ml of liposomal solutions were mixed with 1 ml of Triton X-100 [1% (v/v) in the final solution] to break the liposomes and release the magnetic nanoparticles. A volume of 1 mL of concentrated HCl (37%) was then added to the samples to ionize the iron oxide crystal core and liberate the iron in its ferric state.

The samples were incubated for a few minutes with 3 mL of a 40 mM KSCN aqueous solution. The product of the reaction between the anion (SCN^-) and the Fe^{3+} was a red colored complex – pentaqua(thiocyanate-N) $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$ i.e. $[\text{Fe}(\text{NCS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5]^{2+}$ whose absorbance (ABS) at 480 nm was read using a Carry 60 Agilent UV – vis spectrophotometer [2].

E. Characterization of Nanoparticles

Magnetite (Fe_3O_4) nanoparticles synthesized by this green method were initially examined using Carry 60 Agilent UV – vis spectrophotometer. FT-IR spectroscopy of *Datura innoxia* leaf extract and magnetite nanoparticles was carried out in the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} by Perkin Elmer FT-IR spectrophotometer which confirmed that the protein present in the extract has the ability to act as reducing agent and

stabilizer for Fe_3O_4 nano particles forming protein coated magnetic nano-bio hybrid. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed under nitrogen atmosphere at a heating rate of 10°C/min from room temperature up to 700°C.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Datura innoxia leaves material was collected from the location Latitude: 27N 48' 15.64 and Longitude: 75E 01' 51.36" (FET, Mody University, Lakshmanagarh, Sikar district of Rajasthan province of India). The leaves were dried and later finely powdered for extraction of phytochemicals present in it. Bio-reductive green-synthesized Ferric oxide (Fe_3O_4) nano-bio hybrid was produced by treating ferric ions with the leaves extract of *Datura innoxia*. Ferric chloride was taken as the metal precursor in the present experiments whereas leaves extract act as a reducing as well as a stabilizing agent. The color change was noted by visual observation in the Schott Duran beaker which contains Ferric chloride solution with *Datura innoxia* leaves extract.

The color of the Ferric chloride / leaves extract solution changed from light brown to dark brown after 5 min. This color change indicates the formation of Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles in the solution. The initial pH of the leaf extract was 5.03, whereas that of Ferric and Ferrous chloride was 3. The final pH after the completion of reaction was observed as 10.

The formation of Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles was confirmed by using UV-visible spectroscopy (UV-vis), Fourier-Transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The formation of the Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles was first monitored using UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy. The UV-Vis spectroscopy revealed the formation of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles by exhibiting the typical surface plasmon absorption maxima at 290 nm from the UV-Vis spectrum (Fig. 1) [12].

Fig. 1 UV – visible spectrum of solution after treatment with leaf extracts. The characteristic peak around 290 nm was obtained; confirming the synthesis of magnetite nanoparticles

FTIR spectroscopy was used to identify the functional groups of the active components based on the peak value in the region of infrared radiation. The strong band at 1640.11 cm^{-1} and the shoulder peak at 1411.06 cm^{-1} are identified as the amide I and amide II of the protein, which arise due to -C=O and -NH stretching vibrations in the amide linkage of the protein. The shift of the band from 1,640.11 cm^{-1} to 1,639.21 cm^{-1} was attributed to the binding of a -C=O group with the

nanoparticles. The presence of magnetite nanoparticles can be seen by two strong absorption bands at around 583.45 and 449.69 cm^{-1} which, corresponding to the Fe-O stretching band of bulk magnetite (Fe_3O_4). These results revealed that the C=O groups were bonded on the magnetite particle surface. Overall the observation confirms the presence of protein in leaf extract, which acts as a reducing agent and stabilizer for magnetite nanoparticles (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 (A) FTIR spectrum of dried aqueous extract of *Datura innoxia* leaves. (B) FTIR spectrum of synthesized Fe_3O_4 magnetic nanoparticles

Fig. 3 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) results of magnetic nanoparticles

Fig. 3 revealed the TGA results for these magnetic nanoparticles. An initial weight loss of 6.11% around 120°C was occurred, followed by 9.66%, 2.36% and 5.45% at 340°C, 510°C and 699°C respectively. The final residual left was 76.39%, thus confirming that the protein was conjugated to the magnetic nanoparticles forming the nano-protein hybrid. The initial weight loss of magnetite nanoparticles powder under 100°C is likely to be caused by the contained water.

The protein of *Datura innoxia* leaf extract decomposes completely at temperature higher than 600°C and the residual weight of magnetite nanoparticles is 76.39% at 700°C. The results of TGA illustrated that there is amide I and amide II in *Datura innoxia* leaf extract in the magnetite nanoparticles with

weight is around 34%. Overall the TGA demonstrated that *Datura innoxia* leaf extract existed on the surface of magnetite nanoparticles [5].

The results of FTIR and TGA confirm that protein was coated onto the magnetite nanoparticle surface forming nano-bio hybrid. In the ferrofluid, protein was chemisorbed onto the magnetite nanoparticle surface through their amide carbonyl groups by forming interactions with the Fe atoms as shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Core-shell structure of protein-coated magnetite nanoparticles

Liposomes are just hollow spheres of lipids, i.e. some lipids form membranes that close on themselves forming liposome. Side by side liposome preparation was carried out in which aqueous magnetic fluid was mixed with Oleic acid and Linoleic acid mixture resulting in complete miscible of the oils in organic solvent. During the initial stage of addition of water causes the oil layer to settle down at the bottom of the flask. Once the volatile liquid evaporates completely the oil emulsion starts floating on the surface of the flask forming granules of different sizes attaching to the walls of the flask.

Assay of magnetite nanoparticles encapsulated into liposome was assayed using KSCN. Confirmation of magnetic nanoparticles into liposome was determined by using KSCN.

Addition of liposomal solutions into Triton X-100 causes the disruption of lipid bilayer into small pieces and unilamellar structures. Concentrated HCl ionize the iron oxide crystal core and liberate the iron in its ferric state. The KSCN aqueous solution results into a red colored complex – pentaqua (thiocyanate-N) Fe (III) whose absorbance (ABS) at 480 nm was read using a Carry 60 Agilent UV – vis spectrophotometer (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 Production of red coloured complex – pentaqua (thiocyanate – N) Fe(III) Conclusion

A novel method for complete purification of liposomal entrapped magnetic nano-bio hybrid has been performed as mentioned in Fig. 6. A syringe was filled with the fresh prepared liposomal solution. The syringe is then connected to a flexible plastic tube. The tube is then placed between the poles of a high magnetic field. The other end of the tube is placed in the collector [13].

Fig. 6, Extraction of magnetic liposomes

IV. CONCLUSION

In the present study we report encapsulation of plant protein mediated green synthesis of magnetite nano-bio hybrid into liposome. This involves a green approach for the synthesis of protein coated Fe_3O_4 magnetic nano-bio hybrid using leaves extracts of *Datura innoxia* containing protein which have been found to be very effective stabilizing agent by forming a coating on the surface of the nano particle besides being acting as reducing agent for the formation of magnetite nano particles. A theory and the mechanism have also been proposed for isolation of pure magnetic liposomes. This is the base of our future investigation where drug will be entrapping into magnetic liposome for target delivery. Such hybrid magnetic liposomes can be a robust drug delivery platform with high drug encapsulation yield, tuneable and sustained drug release profile, excellent serum stability, and potential for differential targeting of cells or tissues.

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